

Environmental chemistry education for the 21st Century

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Education plays a critical role in realizing sustainable development and promoting the capability of the people to address environmental/developmental issues. On the verge of the 21st Century, educational reforms and development are placed at a high priority in many countries. In the Asia-Pacific region, a project called "Learning for a Sustainable Environment — Innovations in Teacher Education through Environmental Education" initiated by UNESCO-ACEID has contributed towards the promotion of environmental education, specifically comprehensive one in school. It is also evident that science/chemistry is one of the most important subjects in dealing with environmental education. The relationship between human life and the environment can logically be explained through scientific/chemical skills and knowledge. Accordingly it is required that some chemistry-oriented teaching materials on comprehensive environmental education be effectively implemented in school.

Chemical treatment of waste material and wastewater generated in school laboratories can be the appropriate teaching material for environmental chemistry education, because the treatment involves some typically important chemical reactions such as precipitation, neutralization, oxidation-reduction, and so on. Some reaction cycles for recovering several chemical compounds from wastewater involving iron, manganese, copper and so on are useful to secondary school chemistry as well as introductory general chemistry at colleges and universities. It is important to develop chemical recycling systems for such metallic ions in school laboratories and to introduce the principle of recycling as a practice of environmental protection by students themselves. Such an approach enables students to understand chemical reactions involved and the role of chemistry in preserving our environment, which may in turn lead to environmentally responsible attitudes and actions in their daily lives.

Development in the 20th Century has brought various social and economic benefits to people, but the changes have also caused a range of environmental problems/issues at both local and global levels. On the verge of the 21st Century, people have begun to recognize that one of the most important concerns is the environmental problem, which faces our society. There is no doubt that education plays a crucial role in solving such problems to realize the so-called sustainable environment. 'Agenda 21' of the Earth Summit held in Rio de Janeiro in 1992, declared that education is critical for promoting sustainable development and improving the capability of the people to address environmental and developmental issues^{1,2}.

It must be noted that environmental education aims not only acquiring the content knowledge related to environmental problems in the society, but also fostering students' abilities and attitudes necessary for the precise judgement to solve the problems and for their own decision-making³. The aims are summarized by citing the so-called three aims (3A's) of environmental education, as given in Fig. 1.

In a more concrete way, the objectives of environmental education are given as follows³ :

(i) Awareness : To help students acquire sensitivity to the environment and its attendant problems, develop the

Fig. 1. Three aims of environmental education.

ability to perceive and discriminate among stimuli; process, refine and extend these perceptions; and use this new ability in a variety of contexts,

(ii) Knowledge : To help students acquire a basic understanding of how the environment functions, how people interact with the environment, and how problems/issues dealing with the environment arise and how they can be solved,

(iii) Attitudes : To help students develop a set of values and feeling of concern for the environment and the motivation and commitment to participate actively in environmental protection and improvement,

(iv) Skills : To help students acquire the skills to identify and investigate the environmental problems/issues, and contribute to the resolution, and

(v) Participation : To provide students with opportunities to be actively involved at all levels towards such resolution.

We can say that the ultimate goal of environmental education is to develop people's awareness, competence, attitudes and values, enabling them to be effectively involved in the sustainable development at local, national and international levels, and helping them towards a more equitable and sustainable future^{3,4}.

Environmental education in school

Environmental education has been implemented in many formal and nonformal contexts, currently ranging from school-based environmental curricula to education through mass media. It is important for the young to acquire knowledge, skills and attitudes about and for the environment. Schools, in particular, have an essential role to nurture students to be concerned for and to be committed to maintaining a good or better environment through environmental education.

The first thing to do is to question what to teach for environmental education. For developing an environmentally-literate citizenry, we must foster the versatile abilities required for environmental education. One of the most fundamental abilities is represented as environmental literacy. The author believes that environmental literacy consists of two essential pillars, i.e. scientific literacy and environmental values, and that acquisition of such literacy plays a vital role in achieving the aims of environmental education⁵. The acquisition of environmental literacy contributes not only to the solution of environmental problems but also to the enrichment of one's personality. It is evident that science/chemical education is one of the most important subjects dealing with environmental education. Science/chemistry education provides a good guide to answering environmental questions, tells us how the world works, and explains logically the relationship between human life and the natural environment through scientific knowledge and skills.

Attention is then directed to the question on how to infuse the teaching into the customary school curriculum system. Currently, a curriculum approach, which is characteristic of environmental education for sustainability, is expected in many countries. It develops and combines scientific enquiries, social science thinking and practical skills with the creative and aesthetic sensibilities of the language, arts and so on. Students may be motivated to change their

consciousness when they are scientifically knowledgeable about the degradation of their environment and this may in turn lead to environmental action. However, it is not science that can tell us whether to seek solutions or why we do so. The choice must be made based on personal values, and the resolution of our ecological dilemma requires not only technological changes but also changes in the attitudes and behavior of people. It is important that teachers then allow students to clarify and use such values to make decisions about choosing the alternatives as well as to develop skills based on such values⁴.

As the pedagogy of environmental education instruction, it is necessary to teach students to acquire the following abilities successively³ :

Level 1 : Knowledge about the environment

Level 2 : Values clarification in the environment

Level 3 : Action to be taken for the environment

UNESCO-ACEID project

At the UNESCO/Asia-Pacific Centre of Educational Innovation for Development (ACEID) Seminar held in Tokyo in 1996, participants from the attending countries reported on recent developments in teacher education for environmental education⁶. They agreed that the current priority for environmental education is to consolidate and institutionalize teacher education efforts to ensure that all teachers recognize their potential as environmental educators. Many countries also reported increases in (i) environmental reporting in the mass media, (ii) an expansion of the number of environmental NGOs, (iii) a greater cross-sectional involvement in environmental management, (iv) the 'greening' of industry and commerce, and (v) high level of public involvement in, and responses to environmental campaigns. Despite such achievements, the country reports identified a number of problems which face environmental education. The main problems raised are : (i) environmental education is often not a curriculum priority at the school level, where the curriculum is over-crowded, (ii) the low profile of environmental education in external examinations also causes its lack of status in schools, (iii) there are few qualified teacher trainers for environmental education, and (iv) there are inadequate and insufficient resource materials on environmental education.

Educational systems are responding to this status through increasing support for environmental education in both formal and non-formal education. In some countries, there has been a great increase in the development of environmental education guidelines by education ministries. In addition, recent developments in public environmental awareness and

environmental policy have stimulated developments in teacher education in environmental education. Various organizations have so far recognized the urgent need to develop environmental education in teacher education programs. The UNESCO-UNEP International Environmental Education Programme has recognized preparation of teachers as 'the priority of priorities' for action to improve the effectiveness of environmental education.

In response to such recognition, UNESCO/ACEID continued to promote the development of environmental education in the Asia-Pacific region through the project "Learning for a Sustainable Environment—Innovations in Teacher Education through Environmental Education". The purpose of the project was to expand the range of innovative practices used in teacher education programs in the Asia-Pacific region by introducing teachers and teachers-in-training to the curriculum planning skills and teaching methodologies of environmental education. The prototype teaching modules prepared in 1995 were evaluated, trialed and revised. In late 1997, the sourcebook of environmental education for teachers, which includes ten modules for workshops, was published and the copies were distributed to relevant workers in the region (The modules are accessible through an Internet; <http://www.ens.gu.edu.au/ciree/LSE/Index.html>)⁷. The contents of the modules are given as follows : (1) Education for sustainability, (2) A whole-school approach to environmental education, (3) Experiential learning for the environment, (4) Storytelling for the environment, (5) Indigenous knowledge for the environment, (6) Values education for the Environment, (7) Enquiry learning for the environment, (8) Learning outside the classroom, (9) Community problem solving, (10) Appropriate assessment for environmental education.

We see that these teaching modules were prepared beyond the framework of the existing subjects such as science and social studies. It is also noted that the sourcebook aims to enable students to develop environmental sensitivity, understanding, problem-solving skills and values clarification by using examples from their immediate environment. In addition, it emphasizes the complexity of environmental problems and thus the need to develop critical thinking skills and decision making abilities. It is needed that more such modules will be developed, trialed and disseminated in school.

Educational reforms in Japan

Lately there have been more debate and discussion than ever before regarding the future state of education in Japan². The Central Council of Education, for example, put forward the recommendation for the future state of educa-

tion in Japan. In line with this recommendation, the following points were implemented as an educational target of the revised courses of study, which are to be put forth from 2002 and 2003 at primary schools and junior high schools, and senior high schools, respectively : (i) To introduce education responsive to societal changes resulting from internationalization, information explosion, advance in scientific technology and environmental degradation, (ii) To introduce a new learning area of 'comprehensive learning', (iii) To promote international cooperation in teacher education, (iv) To diffuse environmental education in school to cope with recent environmental degradation, both local and global.

To achieve such objectives, some new approaches such as subjective and experiential lessons beyond the framework of the existing subjects must have to be implemented in school education. The following methodologies are recommended for such education : (a) outdoor education methods, (b) affective education methods, (c) simulation games (including 'Role playing'), (d) case study methods, (e) community resources use and so on⁸. There is also a need to encourage problem-solving learning, cooperative learning, learner-centered learning and experiential learning to inculcate a respect for nature and to develop the higher order thinking and creative skills necessary to protect and manage the environment. Such learning can be put into practice through various activities like decision making, inquiry-based, and audiovisual learning. It is apparent that the development of methodologies of environmental education and the teaching materials focused on the above strategies is urgently needed to promote environmental education in school.

Lately it has been becoming a serious trend that the younger generation is 'shunning' science and technology. To cope with this problem, the author believes that environmental education as well as the so-called Science, Technology and Society (STS) education can play some important roles. There must also be stress regarding the reform in science education that science should be taught not for excellence but for all : universal science should be disseminated. Fig. 2 shows the interrelationship among such education. The relationship between human beings and the environment can logically be explained through scientific/chemical knowledge and skills. Our recent survey revealed that students are interested in such contents related to the environment⁹. In particular, many students reviewed the need for the experiential learning as a strategy of learning. Once they are motivated in such learning, they may develop their learning by themselves which may in turn interest them in science/chemistry learning in school.

Fig. 2. The relationship between comprehensive environmental education and science/chemistry education.

It is thus important for us to develop and diffuse the environment-related science/chemistry teaching modules. By introducing such modules it is expected that students can not only logically understand various environmental problems/issues but also acquire the scientific and chemical literacy. The author believes that it is needed to reform our science/chemistry education in view of environmental education, science/chemistry education for all, and STS education. It must be noted here that in effective dissemination of such education, teacher education should be promoted. It is thus important that environmental education is taught more in pre- and in-service teacher training courses.

International cooperation in the field of environmental education

Here in Hiroshima University, we have had teacher training courses on practice of science education since 1990 in cooperation with the Japan International Cooperation Agency (JICA)¹⁰. The target group has been science teachers working in South-East Asia and Africa. The course on practice of science education is designed to provide secondary school teachers with practical skills on science experiment and observation. Through the training programme, participants are expected (i) to understand the system and teaching methodology of science education in Japan, (ii) to acquire experimental and observational skills in physics, chemistry, biology and earth science, (iii) to develop low-cost materials for science experiments and master the techniques of their practical application, and (iv) to acquire the ability to understand science in a more comprehensive way.

Currently, as a series of the official development assistance (ODA), JICA conducts such activities as training, dispatch of experts, project-type technical cooperation, development study, dispatch of cooperation volunteers and so forth. It is hoped that contents related to environmental education should be implemented in the JICA training programs particularly for secondary school science teachers in the future. Some teaching materials on environmental science/chemistry education developed by the present author and

his coworkers will be shown in a later section.

It is also pointed out that, to sustain such a training program of technical transfer in science education, the following points should be taken into account : (a) to develop instructional materials appropriate for learner-centered learning, (b) to introduce science classes which enable learners to acquire scientific/chemical literacy and make decisions, and (c) to establish science for all or universal science which can be shared in any regions of the world, both developed and developing countries.

In addition, in order to improve instructional contents on comprehensive/integrated topics, environmental education and STS education which deal with multi-sectoral problems/issues should be earmarked as one of the top priority subjects in science education. It is expected that such science learning including environmental education contributes towards the development of students' sense of their rights and responsibilities as global citizens to achieve the sustainable development of environment.

Role of chemistry in environmental education

In view of the author's survey on the past and present status of environmental education in schools, it seems that chemical aspects have not always been reflected in such education, although it is evident that chemistry is one of the most important subjects that should deal with it in schools¹¹. It must be pointed out here that teaching materials for such education have not fully been developed and introduced in school at the secondary and tertiary education levels.

It is interesting to note that lately many chemists have begun to recognize the importance of 'green chemistry'¹². The author believes that we the chemistry educators should promote the 'greening' of chemistry in school. That is, we should substantiate such a concept through our chemistry classes, seeking for environmentally friendly and responsible chemistry. For example, in chemistry laboratories, we could reduce the size of starting chemicals so long as the objectives of the experiments are achieved. We then recover to reuse or recycle the waste material after experiments on the basis of the so-called 4R's (Reduce, Recover, Reuse and Recycle) principle. To reduce the chemicals, we may introduce 'microscale chemistry', which is an environmentally safe pollution prevention method of performing chemical processes using small quantities of chemicals without compromising the quality of education¹³.

In any chemistry laboratory, it is desirable to minimize waste at its source by recovering, reusing or recycling the material. Some examples which seem to be appropriate for classes of environmental chemistry education are given below.

(1) An experiment of heat evolution by use of iron rust formation and subsequent recovery of iron(III) salts :

This heat evolution is utilized for a pocket heater which is commercially available in Japan. This heat evolution is based on the reaction of iron with oxygen and water in air to form iron hydroxide oxide, FeOOH,

It is interesting that the temperature of the reactant mixture rises up to *ca* 330 K or higher in 10–15 min, when a mixture of 12 g of activated carbon, 8.0 g of iron powders and 10 ml of aqueous 10% sodium chloride solution is occasionally stirred with a glass rod in a foam polystyrene cup¹⁴.

In the light of recycling of chemicals used in school laboratories, it is interesting to recover the waste materials, after the rust formation experiment. Students may be asked to think about the method of recovering activated carbon as well as an iron(III) compound and do it by themselves. As one of the possible treatments, students may dispose of the waste chemicals as follows :

(i) To the solid waste (which is a mixture of the product of FeOOH, unreacted Fe, NaCl, C and H₂O) is added water, mixed and filtered when sodium chloride is dissolved away from the solid waste.

(ii) The solid product and unreacted Fe except C are then dissolved in dilute sulfuric acid and the carbon is recovered.

(iii) The filtrate, which contains iron(III) sulfate and iron(II) sulfate, is oxidized with hydrogen peroxide to change iron(II) sulfate to iron(III) sulfate.

(iv) After concentrating and cooling the solution, iron(III) sulfate crystals are obtained.

Alternatively, instead of the procedure (iii), we can add a sodium hydroxide solution to the filtrate to form the precipitate, a mixture of iron(III) hydroxide and iron(II) hydroxide. The precipitate can be recovered for use as starting materials in other laboratory classes.

In relation to the discussion above, it is interesting here to touch on the strength of recycling efficiency in producing iron metal, as the energy required for producing it in the world is tremendously enormous. Table 1 shows the comparison between the production of iron from scrapped iron and iron ore¹⁵. It is noted that by recycling iron we can save much energy and material, and decrease air and water pollutants exhausted. We could also approximately estimate the energy consumptions thermodynamically assuming the following reactions for the two processes :

(a) From iron ore at room temperature to liquid iron at

Table 1 Efficiency of recycling on producing 1 kg of iron

Item	From iron ore	From scrapped iron	Rate of saving in recycling %
Material required*	2 28 kg	0 25 kg	89
Water required*	63 kg	37 kg	41
Energy consumed	25×10 ⁴ kJ	6 4×10 ⁴ kJ	74
Air pollutants exhausted	121 g	17 g	86
Water pollutants exhausted	67 5 g	16 5 g	76

*Material except iron ore and water required for production

the melting point of 1808 K :

(b) From scrapped iron at room temperature to liquid iron at the melting point :

It is seen that theoretically we can save about 68% of energy by producing iron from scrapped iron compared to that from iron ore¹⁶.

(2) Reuse of manganese(IV) oxide used in oxygen evolution :

Manganese(IV) oxide or manganese dioxide (MnO₂) is used as catalyst in evolving oxygen using the reactions,

Waste manganese(IV) oxide is easily recovered after the experiments by washing with water and drying. The recovered MnO₂ is reused repeatedly for the oxygen evolution experiments in other classes. The catalytic powers can be compared between the recovered and commercially available MnO₂, by measuring the rate of decomposition of hydrogen peroxide. Table 2 compares the rate constants between different origins of MnO₂, assuming the first order of reaction¹⁷. It is noted that MnO₂ can be used several times by recovering it. A rather qualitative comparison of the catalytic powers could be made by observing the rate of foaming due to oxygen evolution in a mixed solution of detergent and hydrogen peroxide.

It was also found that if the recovered MnO₂ is heated in

Table 2. Comparison of rate constants k ($\times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$) for decomposition of hydrogen peroxide catalysed by manganese(IV) oxide

Run	MnO ₂ used ^a	Temp K		
		298	308	313
(1)	Reagent grade	3.36	6.47	8.79
(2)	Recovered after run (1) ^b	3.13	5.08	8.20
(3)	Recovered after run (2) ^b	2.92	4.68	5.95

^a50 ml of 0.12 M H₂O₂ solution and 70 mg of MnO₂ (100–170 mesh) were used
^bDried at 313 K for 12 h after suction filtration

a crucible at higher temperatures the catalytic power is more effectively reclaimed.

(3) Reaction involving copper and cycling copper(II) compounds :

It is accepted that the precipitate obtained by mixing a sodium hydroxide solution with a copper(II) sulfate solution is not simply copper(II) hydroxide but basic copper(II) sulfate¹⁸. It should be noted that pure hydroxide solution with a copper(II) hydroxide, Cu(OH)₂, is predominantly formed under the limited condition of preparation. It was confirmed that synthetic brochantite, Cu₄(OH)₆SO₄ or CuSO₄·3Cu(OH)₂, is formed when a copper(II) sulfate solution is titrated slowly with a sodium hydroxide solution at room temperature. Pure copper(II) hydroxide is formed when a tetraamminecopper(II) complex solution is titrated slowly with a sodium hydroxide solution at room temperature. Fig. 3 shows a typical pH-titration curve for the reaction. The fact that the abrupt pH jump at the molar ratio of OH⁻ to Cu²⁺ of 1.5 implies that the composition of the precipitate is not Cu(OH)₂ but Cu₄(OH)₆SO₄. It was reported that synthesis of the basic copper(II) salts is an illustrative teaching material of chemical reactions, because the produced basic salts represent respective characteristic colors. The pH-

Fig. 3. A pH-titration curve for reaction of 1.00 M of copper(II) sulfate solution with 1.00 M of sodium hydroxide solution at room temperature

titrimetry, from which the stoichiometry of the precipitate is deduced, can be a suitable experiment for advanced high school chemistry or first year college chemistry.

It is also interesting that basic copper(II) carbonate, Cu₂CO₃(OH)₂ or CuCO₃·Cu(OH)₂, can be prepared by reacting a copper(II) sulfate solution with a slight excess of sodium carbonate solution at ca. 320 K,

On heating copper(II) hydroxide it decomposes to copper(II) oxide around 450 K,

Basic copper(II) carbonate decomposes thermally to form a solid product, copper(II) oxide evolving water vapor and carbon dioxide^{19–21},

Basic copper(II) sulfate decomposes via a stable intermediate to copper(II) oxide at ca. 1000 K¹⁸,

Fig. 4. TG traces of thermal decompositions of copper(II) hydroxide and basic copper(II) compounds. Sample size, 10.0 mg, heating rate, 10 K/min, atmosphere, N₂ flowing at a rate of 50 ml/min

Fig. 4 shows typical thermogravimetric (TG) curves for the thermal decomposition of the three copper(II) compounds. We see that the mass-loss corresponds to the stoichiometry of each decomposition. Chemical analyses of Cu^{2+} and SO_4^{2-} involved in the starting materials and Cu^{2+} in the decomposition product may be suitable for an introductory undergraduate experiment. It is also interesting that kinetic analysis of such solid-state reactions enables students to appreciate the kinetic process of chemical reactions²²⁻²⁴.

In view of recovering/reuse/recycling, chemical treatments of waste and wastewater produced by chemical experiments in schools are appropriate as teaching materials for environmental chemistry education, because such treatments involve some typically important chemical reactions such as neutralization, precipitation, double decomposition, oxidation-reduction, and so on. The principles of the chemical treatment of waste and wastewater can be discussed in the secondary school chemistry classes, as well as in introductory general chemistry classes at universities. It is noted that such teaching is also of value for pre-service and in-service science teacher education programs. Details of the teaching materials developed by the present author and his collaborators will be published elsewhere.

Fig. 5 illustrates the cycling reactions useful for such a treatment at chemical laboratories in high schools or universities. Firstly, we instructors may ask students about "How could the waste chemicals be disposed of?" They can discuss the principle and method of the treatment using their knowledge and ability. When wastewater containing, for example, Cu^{2+} ion is disposed of, they may come to a conclusion that the ion is removed by precipitation and filtration, which is one of the simplest methods of treatment of wastewater. Before we wash the filtrate into the drain, we must make a qualitative test to confirm that it no longer contains any appreciable Cu^{2+} . It is an added advantage that the solid recovered could be reused as starting material for other reactions of copper(II) compounds.

Fig. 5. A reaction scheme of copper(II) compounds useful for chemistry experiments in school.

It follows that through such lessons, students can learn not only some important contexts of chemistry but also the practical aspects of preservation of our environment. They will also recognize that chemistry can play an important role in preserving our environment. In addition, such an approach will deepen students' awareness of environmental problems. In other words, basic chemical knowledge and skills are required for all to attain the so-called sustainable environment. It is also important for us to see the environment as resources to foster scientific and technological literacy for all.

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